

Theoretical Model for the Physical Vacuum as a Superfluid Medium: Structure, Pair Production, Emergent Gravitation, Light Propagation, and Virtual Particle Creation-Annihilation Processes

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Abstract

We have intuited the structure of a bosonic superfluid medium that has the same behavior as the physical vacuum. Referring to the main known experimental evidences, we describe its basic dynamics. We prove that it is Lorentz-invariant, and that it is possible to adopt an abelian Higgs-type Lagrangian for the description of pairs generation from it. We also prove that from this fluid it is possible to derive Maxwell's equations. We then show that it is possible to describe the behavior of the fluid also with a classical approach. In particular, we have derived a simple classical formula that considers the process through which electron-positron pairs are generated from the vacuum - i.e. from the fluid - starting from the collision of gamma rays. This formula links the mass of the real particles to the electric parameters of the waves and of the fluid which they come from. As result we show that, if we use the same hypothesis used to calculate the classic radius of the electron, we are able to get that precise value, but through a different reasoning. We then provide a physical description of how the gravitational field emerges. In accordance with quantum physics, this fluid medium, that we call Immaterial Fluid, is made up of a discrete number of quantum elements, that we call Immaterial Atoms, IAs. Their variables vary in a continuous way and they undergo spacetime distortions. In accordance with relativity, on a macroscale also the Immaterial Fluid its continuous and undergo spacetime distortions. The set of IAs represents the medium through which waves are transmitted. IAs oscillations during wave transmission are what is identified as the virtual particles that mediate the electromagnetic wave in the vacuum.

Introduction

In analogy with other theoretical frameworks, let's assume the initial hypothesis that the physical vacuum is actually a superfluid medium [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 49, 50]. We call it Immaterial Fluid and we are going to define its structure. We want to prove that, even if we start from this assumption, it is possible to develop a model which is consistent with known physical properties and with major experimental observations. In this perspective, the Immaterial Fluid is the spacetime, i.e. the spacetime is defined by the Immaterial Fluid itself. It is made up of the set of its elementary bosonic particles, the Immaterial Atoms, IAs. We are going to physically describe the structure of the IAs, how electromagnetic waves are transmitted through them, and how virtual particles emerge [77, 79] as IAs excitation. We build two mathematical models. We believe that a description that is possible in multiple distinct ways is technically more robust and deeper than one that is possible only in a way [70, 71]. With the first model we show the Lorentz invariance of the fluid, the energy balance during pairs generation from the vacuum, i.e. from the fluid, and Maxwell's equations as emergent from the fluid. On the other hand, our classical mathematical model predicts the precise situation (Ultimate Equilibrium) in which an electron-positron pair materializes from the vacuum [26, 44] [Fig. 4b]. From this derives the emergence of the gravitational field. The pairs production we describe is due to the inelastic collision of gamma rays [13, 40, 41, 42, 43]. It could be compared to a sort of state transition of the superfluid [51, 52]. We already published on ZENODO an article [24] in which we derive IAs' fundamental equations, the emergence of time from IAs, in which we describe how is physically possible that light always have the same speed. From the physical vacuum as Immaterial Fluid, it is also possible to conceive and easily describe a plausible structure for quarks, gluons, the three generation of charged leptons and quarks, and more [81]. The baryogenesis will be presented in a subsequent work.

Methods

We consider an initial situation, physically contemplable, in which a region of spacetime is represented by the Immaterial Fluid [23, 24], constituted by a network of Immaterial Atom bosons, IAs [23, 24]. We

use the term “immaterial” to indicate that – as for virtual particles - they don’t possess a real (on-shell) mass and we can’t directly perceive them [7]. As we will see, immaterial and virtual particles are related, because, in our model, virtual particles emerge from IAs oscillation during wave transmission. We use the term “immaterial” instead of “virtual” because we consider the immaterial particles as already existent in the Immaterial Fluid. Instead, in conventional quantum field theory, virtual particles are not considered to standalone entities. Rather, they indicate temporary intermediate states in interactions and do not possess independent ontological status [119, 120, 121].

Each IA boson results from the overlap of two immaterial, pure electric charges with opposite sign, i.e. two opposite immaterial charged leptons, each with spin $s=1/2h$. The concept of immaterial, pure electric charge can be considered coherent with that of charge as a quantum excitation [7, 22]. It seems reasonable to compare the pair production to a sort of state transition of the superfluid [51, 52], in which leptons transform from immaterial to real. We can therefore interpret immaterial and real lepton as two distinct phases of the same element. So, we consider them as characterized by the same parameters, except for the mass. In particular, by their electric charge Q_e^+ and Q_e^- , their respective magnetic moment, and spin [122, 123]. Particles possessing intrinsic spin and electric charges have a magnetic dipole moment proportional to their spin, and therefore behave as magnetic dipoles [19, 37]. In this article, we will use the notion of magnetic dipoles of charged leptons to develop the description of the process.

We assume that in the hypothetical absence of electromagnetic waves or quantum fluctuations, respecting Pauli exclusion principle, IAs’ immaterial leptonic charges are in a stable, unperturbed equilibrium (Note A), completely overlapping [9, 10], with the same spin direction [Fig. 4a]. Each charge is totally “masked” by the other. In this condition each IA boson has therefore spin $s=+1h$ or $s=-1h$, zero electric field, zero magnetic field, zero gravitational field [Fig. 4a]. In a fully symmetric state where all fields vanish and no reference interaction is present, mass would not be an observable quantity. It would still exist as a theoretical parameter, but it would not manifest dynamically [14, 114, 115]. So, immaterial leptons don’t have a real (on-shell) mass [7], but only a “potential” one [23]. Due to their zero fields, they can’t interact each other without an external cause [48]. In the reality there is always an external cause, because of the background radiation (Note B).

Electromagnetic fields conditionate the state of vacuum [8, 26, 27, 28, 29], i.e. of the Immaterial Atoms. We consider a possible situation in which the increase of energy leads to the accumulation in small volumes of their electric charges [7, 14, 22, 23]. The passage of electromagnetic energy excites the immaterial leptons constituting the IAs. As we will see, they will tend to oscillate [1, 5, 6, 23, 30] due to the action of the electromagnetic wave. The oscillation procures polarization and vice versa [7, 22]. It is legitimate to assume that IA bosons interact by polarization [7, 14, 22, 26]. In a sort of analogy to a kind of “macro” LQG, when excited they transmit polarization each other [57] with alternated spin direction, $s=+1h$ and $s=-1h$ [Fig. 2]. According to us, the transmission of the electromagnetic wave is the transmission of polarization from one adjacent IA to the next, and so on. So, the oscillation sequence of adjacent IAs – which have alternated spin $s=\pm 1h$ - would be associated with the continuous creation and annihilation of the virtual particles that mediate the wave. The alternation of spins allows us to schematically represent the oscillations of the electric and magnetic fields transverse to the direction of propagation, analogous to the combination of two opposite helicities in a real photon [111, 112, 113] (Note C). Under appropriate and physically consistent conditions, we give a possible description of how virtual particles – i.e. immaterial leptons - become real [73]. Photon description will be hopefully presented in a subsequent work, together with the resolution of the wave-particle duality and of the two-slit experiment.

Polarizations and oscillations of the vacuum, i.e. of the IAs, are also due to the electromagnetic waves that excite IAs. The electric component of the wave acts radially on the immaterial particles constituting

an IA. By definition, the wave's energy, alternately tries to pull the immaterial lepton with opposite charge and to reject the other one. The magnetic component, orthogonal to the electric one, acts on both magnetic dipoles of the immaterial particles, tending to separate them along the spin axis [37, 100, 101, 102, 103] [Fig. 2, 4a]. During this phase IAs charges are partially unmasked and they can interact with the outside, that is they do as virtual particles do. Their separation will be counteracted by the pull of the electric force between the opposite charges and the pull of the magnetic forces between their respective magnetic dipoles (Note D). This means that when the electromagnetic wave forces immaterial IA's leptons to separate each other, it is making a "virtual" work W_{virt} on them [23]. The concept of this work could be related to the mathematical formalism associated to the virtual dipole separation in vacuum polarization [7, 8, 26, 104, 105]. It is counteracted by IA's internal energy E_{int} due to the interaction of the constituting charges. The alternated action of the wave procures alternated displacement of unmasked portions of charge, i.e. the oscillation of the charges, i.e. IAs' oscillation.

When two photon beams collide head-on, they excite the same IA. They transfer their energy in the same spacetime point [84, 85], i.e. they transfer their energy to the same IA. As we will see, at the proper conditions the situation of pair generation is reached (ultimate equilibrium) [Fig. 4b]. Due to the increase of energy, the two leptons are materializing with a reduction of the volume of their electric charge distribution [7, 14, 22, 23]. They appear at the same time [26] and with a common vertex [25, 26] [Fig. 4b]. At the ultimate equilibrium their magnetic poles with coincident sign are overlapping [Fig.4b]. The waves, satisfying both energy and momentum conservation [7], have transferred their energy to the new generated real leptons [23] (note E).

For conceptual clarity, we adopt the working assumption that, within a limited energy regime, each IA can be treated as remaining in a quasi-stable relative configuration, with deviations characterized as perturbative fluctuations. In accordance with relativity, from the perspective of an external observer, the distortions affecting the IAs, while preserving their relative positions within the network, nonetheless correspond to a displacement in spacetime [124]. In analogy to certain superfluid models [77, 78], we assume that their variables vary in continuous way [23, 24]. For what stated so far, on a macroscale could be reasonable to consider that the set of all IAs theoretically acts as a continuous, homogeneous and isotropic superfluid [77, 78] (Note F). As conceived with our basic description, the Immaterial Fluid medium theoretically equals the behavior of the physical vacuum. This implies that it is also characterized by the same values of electrical permittivity ϵ_0 and magnetic permeability μ_0 as the physical vacuum.

Let us now try to set up a basic description that formalizes the wave propagation through the IAs and the behavior of the fluid during contraction and pairs generation. Two adjacent IAs represent the minimum cell to accommodate a wave of unit length [Fig. 2]. They will overall present spin $s=0\hbar$. In a similar way to the Klein-Gordon field [7], we can then introduce a complex scalar field that represents the quantum configuration of two adjacent IAs, when they are subjected to the action of the wave. For what stated above, we assume that the mass term is zero and that the propagation of the wave through IAs is the transmission of the polarization from an IA to the adjacent one and so on. The transmission of the polarization is defined by the wave trajectory [Fig. 2]. It can therefore be described by a wave function $\varphi(x, t) = A \sin(kx - \omega t)$, where A is the amplitude, k wave number, ω angular frequency. This function satisfies the relativistic wave equation $\square \varphi = \left(\frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 - \partial_x^2\right) \varphi = 0$ on the condition that $\omega=ck$ [72]. That is, the polarization must be transmitted at the speed of light.

To model the dynamics of contraction and splitting of IAs we adopt an abelian Higgs-type Lagrangian [68]. A complex scalar field φ describes the pair of adjacent IAs with total spin $s=0\hbar$. The generation of the fermions happens locally, by a fluctuation localized on a single IA. The field, initially extended and neutral, interacts with a gauge field A_μ according to $\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} + |D_\mu \varphi|^2 - V(|\varphi|)$, where

$D_\mu = \partial_\mu + ieA_\mu$ is the covariant derivative and $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic tensor. The self-interaction potential $V(|\varphi|) = \lambda(|\varphi|^2 - v^2)^2 + \delta V(|\varphi|)$, with λ self-interaction constant and $v \neq 0$ vacuum expectation value, has an unstable maximum and a stable minimum [125, 126]. The maximum is with $|\varphi|=0$. We can associate it to the ultimate equilibrium condition (explained in detail later in the Results of this article). From this position, the leptons either return to the initial condition of IA in oscillation state, or they separate. If they separate, the potential presents a minimum with a broken vacuum $|\varphi|=v$, which represents a localized, charged and massive phase. If we properly choose the parameters λ and v , this scheme allows us to describe the transition from a diffuse and neutral configuration to a pair of point-like objects with mass $m=0.511\text{MeV}$, interpretable as an electron and a positron. The construction is formally analogous to that employed in spontaneous symmetry breaking theories U(1) [7, 66, 67, 68].

The phase $\theta(x)$ of the field also interacts with the electromagnetic field A_μ via minimum coupling. The distancing of the immaterial leptons constituting the IAs, due to their oscillation, results in a flow of charge through a space, which we identify with the charge current j^μ . The charge current j^μ can be seen as a manifestation of the fluctuation of the scalar field in a spatial region. It can be written in the form $j^\mu = ie(\varphi^* D^\mu \varphi - \varphi (D^\mu \varphi)^*)$, where the field φ , its complex conjugate φ^* , the covariant derivative D^μ appear [7, 55]. As the distancing of the unmasked leptonic charges increases, their charge distribution will no longer be as uniform as before and an electromagnetic field result [7, 22]. Starting from this framework, since we defined an electromagnetic field tensor and a covariant derivative, it is possible to derive Maxwell's equations as emergent field equations, describing the electromagnetic interaction as a result of the dynamics of the physical vacuum, conceived as the Immaterial Fluid made up of IAs. The charge of each immaterial lepton constituting the IA boson could be theoretically considered variable with variable density [74]. In fact, the current density j^μ associated with the field φ depends on the local phase of φ and the spatial distribution of $|\varphi|$ is variable as long as the IA is extended. When $|\varphi| = v$ the IA is localized and the elements resulting from its splitting can be associated with the defined mass and the fixed electric charge of electron or positron [80].

From the physical vacuum conceived as a superfluid medium constituted by IAs, one can extend a comprehensive mathematical description that is consistent with the formal descriptions currently in use.

Results

We now intend to show how, with the physical vacuum conceived as a fluid medium made up of IAs, it is possible to also develop a classical mathematical analysis in parallel with the covariant and quantum description. Our classical mathematical model (ultimate equilibrium model) tries to describe the physical process during the production of pairs from the vacuum, i.e. from IA bosons. Pair production is a phenomenon that occurs both spontaneously and in particle accelerators [7, 10, 26, 105]. The model considers a precise physical situation (the ultimate equilibrium) in which the two leptons, as written above, transform from immaterial to real, but they are still weakly overlapping [Fig. 4b]. We are going to explain how the different parameters condition the pair generation, to quantify them and to get an important numeric result. The description locally refers to the dynamics due to the interaction of electromagnetic forces. A fundamental role is played by the magnetic dipoles of the leptons [19, 37]. The model is schematized with a macro-interaction between pairs of still immaterial leptons m_{e^+} and m_{e^-} . The dynamic macro interaction is represented by a spring [1, 5, 6]. The reference model is an oscillator with two equal potential masses and three springs with the same elastic constant $k_{v.el.}$ [1, 5, 6] [Fig.1a]. In line with the oscillator models [1, 5, 6], we have represented the charged immaterial particles as points (black balls) m_{e^+} and m_{e^-} [Fig. 1a, 1b]. These "potential charged masses" before reaching the conditions of ultimate equilibrium are to be considered "diffused in a not-deterministic way" [20]. They are not yet

detectable as charged mass. They are confined within the ellipsoidal regions schematized in Fig. 2. These regions of spacetime, and their content in electric charges, as a consequence of the ultimate equilibrium equation (i) are to be considered in dimensional contraction as the frequency of the perturbation wave increases [7, 14, 22, 23] (Note G). Potentially coherent with certain models [66, 95], at the ultimate equilibrium condition a phenomenon of stationary self-localization occurs. The two IA's leptonic charges "collapse" and become real. They are still partially overlapping. That is, they still do not separate and move away each other, but the collapse is happened. If we understand "collapse" as the concentration of the charge density or field in a finite volume, then solitonic solutions too, such as Nielsen–Olesen vortices, could present analogies with this type of configuration. Such solutions are fully compatible with the theoretical framework we used above to model the process, the Abelian Higgs mechanism based on the U(1) gauge symmetry [97, 98, 99].

Let's now describe the IA oscillation, deriving its amplitude φ in term of electric leptonic charges, waves frequency and mass of the generated particles. We consider the forces between the immaterial leptons. As they oscillate, they are partially distinguishing and separating from each other, as described above. We evaluate their elastic oscillation [1, 5, 6]. We consider the moments when only the electric force acts between the immaterial particles. This is because, as we will see later, at the ultimate equilibrium the main magnetic force between the immaterial leptons cancels out [Fig. 4b]. We impose that in this condition the electric force is equal to the elastic one, so $F_{elastic} = F_{electric}$. With simple steps we then find the relationship between the amplitude of the oscillation, the mass generated, and the electromagnetic parameters that characterize the IA when is excited by the wave.

Fig.1a

Fig.1b

We can write $\nu_0 = \sqrt{\frac{k_{v.el.}}{m_e}}$ and $k_{v.el.} = \frac{F_{el}}{\varphi}$, where ν_0 is the "natural" frequency of oscillation – or pulsation- of the (immaterial) virtual dipole [106, 107, 108, 109], which coincides with the frequency of the wave [Fig.2]. F_{el} is the elastic force between the immaterial leptons when they are unmasked, thus at the ultimate equilibrium. Let us impose $F_{elastic} = F_{electric} = K_0 \frac{Q_e^+ * Q_e^-}{\varphi^2}$, where K_0 is Coulomb's constant. We get $k_{v.el.} = \frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{\varphi^3}$ and $\nu_0^2 = \frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{\varphi^3 * m_e}$. From this we get $\varphi = \sqrt[3]{\frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{\nu_0^2 * m_e}}$, which we will call Ultimate Equilibrium Equation (i).

Fig. 2

Fig. 2 Basic scheme of the propagation of the wave through adjacent IAs.

Two adjacent IAs represent the minimum cell to contain the wave length due to the quantum of action [56]. The action of the wave procures IAs' polarization, oscillation and distortion. Polarization is transmitted from an IA to the next adjacent one, and so on. Following the red line in figure, we can intuitively infer how the alternated electric field conditions the IAs, characterized by alternated spin $s=+1h$ and $s=-1h$. The blue line makes evident the magnetic action.

This simple mathematical model finds an important theoretical confirmation when it is imposed that the ellipsoidal regions under examination become spherical, i.e. $\varphi = r$ [Fig. 2]. By doing so we get the frequency ν_0^* , which we call frequency of ultimate equilibrium. At this frequency, when the electromagnetic waves which excite the IAs of the spacetime collide on the same IA, they bring it to the condition of ultimate equilibrium and a pair is generated. Adopting then the same, unrealistic hypothesis used for the calculation of the classic radius of the electron, it is possible to show the internal coherence of our model. In fact, with this hypothesis, the two generated leptons will have the precise value of the classic radius of the electron (and of the positron). At this frequency ν_0^* , a real electron-positron dipole will be perceivable, which translates into the creation of a matter-antimatter pair. Their mass is generated by the effects on the surroundings IAs procured by charges densification, i.e. by the concentration of large quantities of energy in a small volume.

If $\varphi < r$ we could talk about virtual dipole [106, 107, 108, 109]; when $\varphi > r$ of real dipole (with creation of electron and positron); when $\varphi = r$ we will talk about dipole in ultimate equilibrium.

To develop our analysis, we define a “diametrical circumference of the equivalent bosonic sphere”, hereafter simply referred to “equivalent bosonic circumference”, and two “equivalent leptonic spheres”. They represent the charge distribution respectively of the IA boson and of the two real leptons generated by it [23, 24]. This is an abstraction that we use to simplify the description of the physical behavior of the IA and of the real leptons. Let us show that, starting from the vacuum as a fluid made up of IAs, through the ultimate equilibrium model it is possible to develop a coherent classical mathematical analysis. To do

this we take the classical radius of the electron as a reference, $r_{cl} = \frac{Q^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 m_e c^2} \approx 2,818 * 10^{-15}m$. It does not correspond to a physical size of the electron, which is regarded as point-like in QED, but serves as a useful length scale in classical and semiclassical calculations (e.g. scattering Thomson) and indicates the scale below which renormalization effects come into play [86, 87]. Let us then assume the same

unrealistic hypothesis that is used in the classical calculation of the electron radius. That is, we consider the charge of the boson, which is overall null but polarizable, uniformly distributed along the equivalent bosonic circumference. The charge of the leptons, each uniformly distributed on the surface of the sphere by which leptons are mathematically represented [37]. Under this condition, we can demonstrate that the radius of the equivalent leptonic sphere generated by the ultimate equilibrium mechanism coincides exactly with the classical radius of the electron.

Based on the schematic description of the process introduced on Methods, the peripheral speed of transmission of the polarization, $w=c$, will have a “bosonic circular” component, and a “fermionic translational” one due to distancing of the forming leptons during the oscillation. At the ultimate equilibrium, as already described, the collapse of the charges occurs. In this condition, the oscillation is characterized by an amplitude which also depends on the dynamic of concentration of the charge in a small volume. Before the ultimate equilibrium, the (overall zero) charge distribution of the boson is mathematically assumed to be ellipsoidal. In order to simplify, we describe it by the equivalent bosonic circumference, which is endowed with an “equivalent rotation” around its own spin axis, on the plane perpendicular to it. We define X as the characteristic radial dimension of the boson, which would be mathematically representative of the distribution of its charge during wave transition. The equivalent rotation of the IA boson is the theoretical rotation of the boson around its spin axis, with its angular speed ω_{eq} , with its peripheral speed $c = \omega_{eq} * X$ (a) equal to the light speed and with a period t_o equal to the time the wave in all its length needs to be transmitted through it. During the same period t_o , in the reality, the wave transits through two adjacent IAs [Fig. 2]. We assume therefore that two adjacent IAs are the minimum cell that accommodate the wave length of a quantum of action [56]. Peripheral speed equal to the light speed means that the propagation of the polarization between adjacent IAs is the transmission of the wave. By definition it is $v_{eq} = v_0$, i.e. the bosonic equivalent rotation has the same frequency of the wave. Thus, $\omega_{eq} = 2\pi v_{eq} = 2\pi v_0$, where v_0 is the frequency of the wave that perturbs the IA or the equivalent bosonic circumference. At the ultimate equilibrium, due to the collapse, we consider that the characteristic dimension of the equivalent bosonic circumference is going to coincide with the radius of the electron (and positron) that will be generated. At the ultimate equilibrium we can therefore write $X \rightarrow r_{el}$, where r_{el} is the radius of the leptonic sphere. The boson, deformed by the wave, is collapsing. The two leptonic charges arise and waves cannot be transmitted anymore [7, 26] [Fig. 4b]. Ellipsoidal bosonic charge distribution, given by the overlap of the opposite leptonic charge distribution, tends to become two spherical leptonic charge distributions [Fig. 4b].

From these considerations, as a first step we are going to mathematically derive the speed with which the polarization propagates through the boson, i.e. the speed of light. Then, independently, we are going to derive the classical radius of the electron.

Considering the hypothesis of polarization transmission along the equivalent circumference, from (a) we can write $c = 2\pi v_0 * X$. Then, considering the wave length $\lambda_0 = 1/v_0$, if we impose that $X = \lambda_0/2\pi$, we easily get the fundamental relation for electromagnetic waves in vacuum $c=\lambda_0 v_0= \lambda v$ (Note H). These concepts will be further elaborated in other works.

Let's now calculate the classic radius of the electron. We consider the theoretical ellipsoid equation describing the bosonic charge distribution [Fig. 2]:

$$\frac{x^2}{A^2} + \frac{y^2}{B^2} + \frac{z^2}{C^2} = 1$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} A = B = \frac{w}{\omega_{eq}} \quad (b) \\ C = \sqrt[3]{\frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{v_0^2 * m_e}} \end{array} \right.$$

in which w is the speed of transmission of the polarization, so $w = c$.

By analogy with the hypothesis for the calculation of the classic radius of the electron, let's assume that the boson's null charge is uniformly distributed on the equivalent bosonic circumference and consider the equation (b). That is, two opposite leptonic charged circumferences are overlapping, rotating in the same direction. In this way the polarization between adjacent IAs is considered as transmitted through their circumferences [Fig. 2]. As assumed before, during the oscillation, in the reality, each ellipsoidal leptonic charge distribution constituting the IA tends to become spherical and it is distributed also inside the volume, not only on the surface. As described above, when the charges collapse occurs, this spherical distribution becomes concentrated, and the two leptons, even if are still weakly overlapping, can be considered as real.

The bosonic charge distribution - represented by the equivalent bosonic circumference - will deform until it collapses into the two new generated charged leptons, represented by the two equivalent leptonic spheres. Each new generated leptonic sphere has an equivalent angular speed $\omega_{el} = 2\pi\nu_{el}$. We impose that after the collapse $\nu_{el} = \nu_0/2\pi$ (c), where ν_0 is the frequency of the wave that led to the ultimate equilibrium. The hypothetical rotation of the lepton will therefore have a frequency ν_{el} that is smaller than the frequency ν_0 related to the colliding waves or to the equivalent rotation of the bosonic circumference. When the collapse occurs, it is possible to write $\omega_{eq} \rightarrow \omega_{el}$. Referring to xy plane, equation (b), after the charges' collapse, will indicate the radius of each leptonic sphere, perpendicular to its spin axes. Similarly to the IA, ω_{el} indicates the "equivalent rotation" of the lepton around its spin axis. Through (c), (b) numerically becomes

$$A = B = \frac{c}{\omega_{el}} = \frac{c}{2\pi\nu_{el}} = \frac{c}{\nu_0}$$

It derives that, at the ultimate equilibrium, the peripheral speed of the equivalent leptonic sphere is still c . This value cannot be considered realistic, but the classic radius too cannot be considered realistic, because its theoretical peripheral speed would be even bigger than c [88]. In these passages we are only proving the theoretical coherence of a classical description of a model, i.e. the physical vacuum as a fluid medium made up of IAs, whose behavior and energy balance it is been already defined above.

As previously mentioned, let's now impose that at the ultimate equilibrium the radius of the collapsing

bosonic sphere (b) is equal to the amplitude (i) $\varphi = \sqrt[3]{\frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{v_0^2 * m_e}}$ of the oscillation of the two immaterial

leptons [Fig. 4b]. To obtain the classical radius, we equate the radius of the collapsing boson to that of the electron that is formed. The radius of the boson derives from kinematic considerations regarding the transmission of the polarization, i.e. of electromagnetic waves. The radius of the leptons derives instead from the dynamics of the oscillation of the immaterial pair, imposing that the amplitude of the oscillation at the ultimate equilibrium coincides with the radius r_{el} of the leptonic sphere [Fig. 4b].

With these conditions we get the value ν_0^* of the frequency of the waves that lead to the ultimate equilibrium. From this frequency, the precise value of the classic radius of the electron is then obtained (Note I). Thus, $r = A = B = \frac{c}{\nu_0}$ and $\varphi = C$. Imposing $r = \varphi$, we get $\nu_0^* = \frac{m_e * c^3}{K_0 * Q_e^2}$ (ii), which we call "Ultimate Equilibrium Frequency". Its value is $\nu_0^* = 1,0638E + 23$ 1/s.

$m_e = 9,1094E-31$ Kg is the mass of the electron (and positron), $c = 2,9979E+08$ m/s is the light speed, $K_0 = 8,9876E+09$ N* (m² / c²) is Coulomb's electrostatic constant, $Q_e = -1,6022E-19$ C is the charge of the electron.

Replacing ν_0^* in the expressions $r = \frac{c}{\nu_0}$ and $\varphi = \sqrt[3]{\frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{\nu_0^2 * m_e}}$, in both cases we get exactly the precise value of the classic radius of the electron, i.e. $r_{el} = \varphi = 2,818E - 15$ m.

In the table below we report the values of r and φ as the frequency ν_0 varies. It is highlighted that for small values of the frequency (or pulsation), the radial size of the IAs – in the order of thousands of km – is theoretically much larger than the amplitude of the oscillation. For pulsation values higher than those of ν_0^* the graph of Fig. 3 no longer refers to the real case because beyond that threshold we no longer have two bound overlapping immaterial particles, but two real ones that separate. At the ultimate equilibrium frequency we get instead $r_{el} = \varphi = 2,818E - 15$ m, i.e. the classic radius of the electron.

	ν_0 [1/s]	r_e [meters]	φ [meters]	LOG(r)	LOG(φ)
1	1,0638E+01	2,8181E+07	1,3080E+00	7,45	0,12
2	1,0638E+03	2,8181E+05	6,0714E-02	5,45	-1,22
3	1,0638E+05	2,8181E+03	2,8181E-03	3,45	-2,55
4	1,0638E+07	2,8181E+01	1,3080E-04	1,45	-3,88
5	1,0638E+09	2,8181E-01	6,0714E-06	-0,55	-5,22
6	1,0638E+11	2,8181E-03	2,8181E-07	-2,55	-6,55
7	1,0638E+13	2,8181E-05	1,3080E-08	-4,55	-7,88
8	1,0638E+15	2,8181E-07	6,0714E-10	-6,55	-9,22
9	1,0638E+17	2,8181E-09	2,8181E-11	-8,55	-10,55
10	1,0638E+19	2,8181E-11	1,3080E-12	-10,55	-11,88
11	1,0638E+21	2,8181E-13	6,0714E-14	-12,55	-13,22
12	1,0638E+23	2,8181E-15	2,8181E-15	-14,55	-14,55
13	1,0638E+25	2,8181E-17	1,3080E-16	-16,55	-15,88
14	1,0638E+27	2,8181E-19	6,0714E-18	-18,55	-17,22
15	1,0638E+29	2,8181E-21	2,8181E-19	-20,55	-18,55
16	1,0638E+31	2,8181E-23	1,3080E-20	-22,55	-19,88
17	1,0638E+33	2,8181E-25	6,0714E-22	-24,55	-21,22
18	1,0638E+35	2,8181E-27	2,8181E-23	-26,55	-22,55

Fig. 3 Trend of the values of $\log(r_{el})$ and $\log(\phi)$ as the frequency ν_0 of the two waves varies. With reference to the values reported above Fig. 3, it is highlighted that at the ultimate equilibrium frequency $\nu_0^*=1,0638E+23$ 1/s, the value of the radius r_{el} of the real electron (and positron) coincides with the value of the ultimate equilibrium distance ϕ . It turns out $\log(r_{el}) = \log(\phi) = -14,55$, which corresponds to $r_{el} = \phi = 2,818E - 15\text{m}$, i.e. the classic radius of the electron.

The separation of the leptons, starting from the initial complete overlap [Fig. 4a], begins at the ultimate equilibrium distance, which occurs when the magnetic dipoles of the immaterial particles have forcibly translated until they have two overlapping magnetic poles with the same signs [Fig. 4b]. Up to an infinitesimal earlier, theoretically, the action between the magnetic dipoles of the particles recalls the starting position and favors the restoration of the initial configuration of overlapping electric charges (annihilation). An infinitesimal beyond the ultimate equilibrium distance, theoretically, the action between the magnetic dipoles becomes repulsive for the two still overlapping, real leptons, which at this point separate and manifest themselves in spacetime. In a previous article [23], we basic described how, during the transition situation at the ultimate equilibrium, the actual behavior could also give rise to a kind of Zitterbewegung phenomenon [11, 12, 110], then followed by annihilation or separation of the generated particles. As the ultimate equilibrium, it can be considered related both to virtual [12] or real [110] particles.

Each equivalent leptonic sphere hypothetically represents a lepton modeled as a spherical surface charge distribution. Its theoretical rotation is constructed to reproduce the same physical effects as those attributed to the real lepton. The primary effect considered is the intrinsic angular momentum, i.e. the spin. Although spin is not the result of spatial rotation in quantum theory, the model is formulated to formally recover its observable effects.

The classic radius of the electron $r_{cl}=2,818 * 10^{-15}\text{m}$ has historically been calculated by assuming a uniform distribution of charge on a spherical surface. It is obtained by imposing that the electrostatic energy U of a sphere of radius r_{cl} is equal to the rest energy of the electron $E=mc^2$ [37]. It is only a theoretical reference, because if the rotating electron really had that radius, its peripheral speed would be much greater than the speed of light [88].

Fig. 4a

Fig. 4b

Fig.4a Almost stable, unperturbed equilibrium configuration of the IAs, that is quasi-static equilibrium [61, 62, 136]. Situation in a vacuum with weakly curvature, little disturbance waves, subdominant fluctuations. That is, almost in the absence of oscillations. The drawing is not to scale.

Fig.4b “ultimate equilibrium” configuration at the moment of generation of electron e^- and positron e^+ . The particles become real after the total and permanent separation of their electric charges from a common vertex [25, 26]. The action of the overlapping equal magnetic poles forces this dynamic. If there is no separation, they immediately annihilate and return to being IA, or there is the brief Zitterbewegung [11, 12, 23, 110] phase, and after that they return to being IA.

According to us, from the actual physical point of view, in the reality the electron will have a smaller radius than the classic radius and its charge will not be uniformly distributed on the spherical surface, as in the calculation of the classical radius [37].

We propose the following interpretation. Virtual (immaterial) and real particles have a mathematical similar behavior in interactions [14, 15]. In particular, as discussed in the article, when energy increases, the dimensions of the immaterial particles decrease. According to several theories, real electron has an internal structure and it is not punctiform [16, 17, 38, 39]. Measurements of the electron dimensions in accelerators are made at very high energy values, and these values are more and more increasing. The more energy on the tests we provide the smaller the dimensions of the particles we can study, but at the same time no internal structure has been observed for the lepton so far [89]. From these considerations, in analogy with other studies [21, 142], it is possible to hypothesize that, theoretically, the more energy on tests we provide to observe the electron, the smaller its electric charge distribution becomes, preventing us from measuring it.

Let’s now hypothesize that the radius of the electron is actually measured experimentally. Based on what we have seen so far, we establish a distribution of electric charge that would allow us to justify that experimental value. With the aforementioned hypothesis of the electron having an internal structure, one should assume a charge distribution also inside the spherical volume, not only on the surface. Let us assume that the actual charge distribution is spherical. Theoretically, it could also be different from spherical, e. g. a fat torus. We consider that the radius of this sphere has the experimental value R . Let us assume a charge distribution $\rho(r)$ inside the sphere of radius R . The electrostatic energy formula for a sphere with radial charge density is

$$U = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^R V(r) \rho(r) 4\pi r^2 dr$$

where $V(r)$ is the electrostatic potential generated by the charge distribution up to radius r . Let us now look for a charge density $\rho(r)$ that gives an electrostatic energy of value $U = \frac{Q_e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 R}$. Let us assume a charge density increasing with the radius $\rho(r) = \rho_0 \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^n$ where ρ_0 is the maximum density at the edge of the sphere. n , based on R , is an exponent to be determined. It means that it would be possible to theoretically justify an experimental value of the radius R (Note L).

The value of the ultimate equilibrium frequency $\nu_0^* = 1,0638E+23$ 1/s belongs to gamma ray range. The corresponding energy transported by the two incident photon beams is $E = 2h\nu_0^* = 880\text{MeV}$. It produces the virtual work W_{*virt} to win the internal attractive energy E_{int} and to reach the ultimate equilibrium. If separation occurs, it also concentrates the amount $E = 1,022\text{MeV}$ as rest mass of the generated real particles (1 electron + 1 positron) [2]. If separation doesn't occur, two photon beams will be perceivable [69].

These values are calculated starting from the stable, unperturbed equilibrium condition. The ultimate equilibrium frequency could represent kind of a resonance frequency. In reality, even in accelerators or at subnuclear level, energy fluctuations that influence observables and behaviors will always be present [47, 48]. Even the mere presence of measuring instruments theoretically conditions spacetime (IAs) curvature [137, 138]. The conditions for the generation of pairs can also be achieved with other energy values, even lower [40]. On our view, this happens because where the energy fluctuations locally concentrate an energy value close to the minimum for the separation of the leptons, at that point a small transfer of energy, at the very least 1,022MeV, would be enough to free the leptons contained in the IA and produce the pair [139].

The following passage lays the possible foundations to describe the emergence of the gravitational field. Further details will be developed in a subsequent article. From the ultimate equilibrium, if the separation of the real leptons occurs, they repel each other in opposite directions [Fig. 4b]. Since they both have spins aligned in the same direction, and they move in opposite directions, they helicities will be opposite [127], i.e. +1/2 and -1/2. The initial spin/angular momentum of the IA boson is conserved and redistributed between the intrinsic spins of the fermions and their relative orbital angular momentum [82, 83]. For what stated above, when the energy of the wave is absorbed by the pair-generating IA, it implies a concentration of energy in a smaller volume. The surroundings IAs, in contrast, expand their effective volume, because energy is transferred from them to the pair-generating IA [26, 40, 128]. When the particle becomes real, the generated lepton carries furthermore a free charge. This induces polarization of the surrounding IA bosons, in agreement with vacuum polarization effects predicted by quantum electrodynamics [10, 26]. The opposite charges present inside the involved IAs are attracted towards the generated particle, while the charges of the same sign are instead repelled. The consequent IAs deformation results in a continuous redistribution of energy and charge throughout the system [7, 10, 26]. Thus, in analogy with observable superfluids [129], which maintain continuity through collective interactions, the system remains continuous, as assumed in the initial hypotheses. IAs polarization around the generated lepton is persistent, with the deformation oriented toward the center of its electric field [25, 45]. From this perspective, the energy of the electromagnetic field generated by the elementary electric charge contributes to spacetime curvature [132, 133, 134, 135]. Similarly to concepts consolidated in various field [129, 130, 131], this polarization pattern, not the individual bosons, propagates with the particle as it moves, maintaining continuity in the Immaterial Fluid. IA bosons, as specified in Methods, keep their own position in the network. Their deformation, due to the transit of the particle, we physically interpret as the spacetime curvature associated with the gravitational field of the particle. Its magnitude is assumed to correspond to the inertial behavior of the electron's rest mass, 0.511MeV. With the motion of the particle always new IAs dilatate, because of its gravitational field. When the particle moves away

from a region, IAs of that region are not considerably under the effect of its gravitational field anymore. They maintain their respective position in the network, and their characteristic dimension and charge distribution return to what they were before the dilatation [129, 130, 131].

Conclusions

We have described the physical structure and behavior of an immaterial superfluid that behaves like the physical vacuum. We have described the propagation of light through the fluid, the generation of pairs from the fluid, the birth of the gravitational field as an emergent property. For the mathematical description we have developed both a covariant, quantum model and a classical model. These models seem to be further developable, which is beyond the scope of the present work. In addition to a description of spontaneous symmetry breaking analogous to a U(1) Higgs abelian theory, we have developed a classical model that describes the oscillation [1, 5, 6] of the IA on which two waves collide, in the act of transforming its two immaterial leptons into two real leptons with mass. From this, starting from the proper hypothesis, we coherently calculated the classical radius of the electron (and of the positron).

From the formula of the ultimate equilibrium frequency (ii) we can derive the link between the rest mass of the electron or positron and the frequency of the electromagnetic waves that generate it. That is, we

can write E^* as a function of ν_0^* : $\nu_0^* = \frac{m_e * c^3}{K_0 * Q_e^2}$ (ii) $\Rightarrow \nu_0^* = \frac{(m_e * c^2) * c}{K_0 * Q_e^2} \Rightarrow \nu_0^* = \frac{E^* * c}{K_0 * Q_e^2} \Rightarrow$

$$E^* = \frac{K_0 * Q_e^2}{c} * \nu_0^* = 0,511 \text{ MeV} \quad (\text{iii})$$

The aforementioned equations could describe in a simplified way a sort of “wave collapse” through which, among all the possible configurations, i.e. among all the modes of oscillation [1, 5, 6] that are produced by the dynamic interaction of the two IA’s immaterial leptons, in the situation of ultimate equilibrium they find the suitable arrangement to materially manifest themselves in spacetime as real particles. The importance of formula (iii) is that, starting from electromagnetic parameters such as electric charge, Coulomb’s constant, wave frequency, speed of light $c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}}$, for the electron/positron the precise value of the energy related to its mass $E=0.511\text{MeV}$ it is been calculated.

This suggests that to obtain further experimental confirmation of the creation of electrons and positrons from the collision of electromagnetic waves in a vacuum, it could make sense to collide two perfectly aligned gamma ray beams from opposite directions, with the frequency of ultimate equilibrium $\nu_0^* = 1,0638 * 10^{23} \text{ 1/s}$. We could theoretically expect that a peak of production appears. Due to positive or negative fluctuations [63, 64, 65], as discussed in Methods and Results, it could make sense to try also in a range around the value of the ultimate equilibrium frequency. If possible, it could be reasonable to try with different phases and different circular polarizations too. Examples of similar or connectable experiments are underway at the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (Rhic) at Brookhaven National Laboratory [3], in the United States, or also at the National Graphene Institute in the United Kingdom, at the University of Manchester, where they have observed the Schwinger effect in a device based on graphene superlattices [4]. In 1997 the pairs production due to the collision of gamma rays it is been observed in SLAC particle accelerator [13]. Other related theories and experiments had been made during the years [40, 41, 42, 43] (Note M).

The considerations present in this article are made starting from the main known experimental observations, so consistent with them. They are coherent both with relativity and other theories that consider the physical vacuum as a fluid medium [32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 49, 50]. Assuming therefore, within certain energetic limits, that the physical vacuum of spacetime is the Immaterial Fluid we have presented, we provided a physical description – and not only a mathematical one – of how pairs are generated from the fluid, the relationship between their mass and the electromagnetic parameters of the waves and of the fluid which they come from, and how their gravitational field emerges. With this interpretation, the production of pairs could be compared to a sort of state transition of the superfluid [51, 52]. From the hypothesis of a universe made up of IAs, many other reasonable, clear and simple interpretations for not yet clarified phenomena in physics follow (Note N). These studies have not yet been published, but we will show them as soon as we will complete them.

An experiment sufficient to highlight the presence of the Immaterial Fluid could consist of colliding two laser beams on a screen. The beams should form an angle of almost 180° between them. The cross-section of the beam should be non-point-like, such as a segment or a circle. The lasers are then positioned so that the figures projected on the screen intersect. A line at each segment, or the outline of the intersecting figure must be drawn on the screen. Finally, the entire device is rotated, keeping the relative positions of all the components fixed. According to modern physics, the described experiment will not show any observable physical changes [19, 104, 140, 141]. If a small displacement of the projected beams with respect to the traces left on the screen in the previous configuration will be observed, or an alteration of the current figures in the area of the overlapping beams, it would be therefore sufficient to highlight the presence of the Immaterial Fluid (Note O).

Notes

A The stable, unperturbed equilibrium [23] is a hypothetical condition. In the spacetime of the considered region, i.e. in the considered region of Immaterial Fluid, there are no gravitational or electromagnetic fields, there is no background radiation, there is no form of quantum fluctuations.

B IAs are surrounded by other IAs and overlapping them. Theoretically, when they are in the same stable, unperturbed equilibrium state, without the presence of electromagnetic waves or quantum fluctuations, they can't manifest their mass, because they all have zero electromagnetic fields and they all have the same energy level [14, 23, 114, 115]. This implies that they all have the same characteristic dimension and the same behavior [23, 24]. In these conditions an IA have no possibility to interact with other IAs [48]. Due to waves transmissions, out of the stable, unperturbed equilibrium state, they instead manifest their virtual, temporary mass [7]. They temporarily alter their immaterial leptons complete overlap, temporarily revealing portions of unmasked charges, that temporarily condition the surrounding IAs. Instead, when IA's immaterial leptons become real [23, 26] and separate, their own charge is totally unmasked and permanently conditions the surrounding IAs. As we will see further in this article, the charge, permanently free from masking and with reduced dimensions, polarizes and deforms the surroundings IAs, contributing to the effective inertial and gravitational properties of the system. In this article we propose a possible description of how a permanent, real mass can be generated from an IA excited by colliding photon beams.

IAs have two virtual (immaterial), “potential” masses that under the right electromagnetic conditions become real [23, 26].

C The polarization mainly acts between adjacent IAs making them oscillate [7, 22]. Wave transmission is interpreted as the propagation of polarization from one IA boson to the next one and so on. This dynamic seems to have analogies with LQG [57]. Secondary oscillations are theoretically conceivable [31]. The Immaterial Fluid made up of IAs, characterized by the same behavior of the vacuum, is therefore as full of fluctuation as the vacuum is. Among all the possible paths through the IAs network, energy follows a preferential one, i.e. the transmission of polarization involves an optimal sequence of adjacent IAs, with alternated spin $s=+1\hbar$ and $s=-1\hbar$ [Fig. 2].

When we say that virtual particles mediate the wave transmission, we could actually interpret the phenomenon according to this basic description. When the polarization is transmitted through adjacent IAs, their constituting immaterial leptons oscillate. Their unmasked portions of opposite charges partially and temporarily distinguish each other. This mechanism is transmitted by polarization from an IA to the next adjacent one, and so on, in the direction of propagation of the wave. Thus, the temporary presence of unmasked portions of charges modifies the quantum fields and vacuum fluctuations, leading to observable effects, such as the Casimir effect or the Lamb shift. We identify this process as the creation and annihilation of virtual particles.

D This dynamic is necessarily presented here at a basic level. In another article adequate mathematical insights could be developed.

E Starting from the Immaterial Fluid, also other mechanisms for pair to be produced are theoretically conceivable [81]. One of them is briefly introduced in Note E of Ref. 81.

F Since IA bosons undergo quantum energy fluctuations that give rise to coherent and manipulable states, they can be treated analogously to bosonic modes used as qubit operators [22]. In this framework, quantum overlap between IA bosons becomes possible [18, 19]. Furthermore, their physical variables vary in a continuously way [23, 24]. Similarly to what occurs in superfluids or coherent bosonic condensates, these conditions support the hypothesis of continuity of the Immaterial Fluid [116, 117, 118].

We can therefore consider a three-dimensional network made up of a discrete number of IAs [23]. They are more or less overlapping. In analogy with similar models, we can think of regions hypothetically characterized by a higher or lower density of overlapping bosons [76]. We could consider the possibility that they have variable electric charge and variable density of electric charge [74]. Charge density could be theoretically regarded as a fundamental variable [75]. It appears legitimate to assume that each IA may at the same time undergo gravitational distortions and convey electromagnetic waves [61, 62].

G In a subsequent article, we will derive the fundamental laws that describe the behaviour of IAs and we are going to prove that IAs distortions it is due to the conservation of their spin. We are going to describe the emergence of time and, in more than one way, we are going demonstrate that through IA bosons light will necessary have always the same speed c . From this we can prove why Michelson-Morley experiment failed. This new article will be a development and a clarification of previous articles [23, 24] we published in 2025 on ZENODO.

H In wave transmission, saying that the equivalent bosonic circumference has an equivalent radius $X = \lambda_0/2\pi$, where λ_0 is the length of the wave acting on the IA, is to say that the equivalent bosonic circumference is exactly as long as the wavelength on the Cartesian plane.

I The oscillation frequency of the virtual dipole coincides with the frequency of the electromagnetic wave that excites it [Fig. 2]. At the ultimate equilibrium, as the charges distribution, even before the collapse, tend to become spherical, it also corresponds to the frequency ν_{eq} deriving from the equivalent rotation angular speed ω_{eq} of the IA boson [Fig. 2, 4b].

L The radius of the proton has been determined experimentally, always at low energies and with an uncertainty that varies depending on the experiment conducted [90, 91]. In all cases, however, the order of magnitude remains 10^{-15}m . Let's suppose that the radius of the electron can be measured experimentally and that it is much smaller than the radius of the proton. One could justify the hypothetical experimental value of the two generated leptons, compared with the real size of the proton, by considering a particular description of quarks and gluons based on the physical vacuum conceived as the Immaterial Fluid constituted by IAs [81]. For the Standard Model, gluons are point-like and their action manifests itself in a volume of spacetime [96]. Similar to IAs, according to our interpretation, gluons would be identified with the volume of spacetime characterized by the partial overlap of opposite leptonic real charges [81]. This volume, which can undergo spacetime distortions, could be considered as defined by physical quantities very similar to those of the IAs that surround it [81]. From what we have seen so far, IAs can be considered more dilated than the real lepton, even by a lot. Their immaterial leptonic charge has a lower density than the real one. Similarly, one could assume that gluons also reflect this behavior. As the real leptons partially overlap, the overlapping volume, i.e. the gluons, undergo a big dilatation [81]. According to the same model, quarks would be given by the portion of real leptonic charge free from overlapping [81]. In this way, a possible divergence of several orders of magnitude between the measured radii of proton and electron could be theoretically justified [81].

M In a series of experiments for the detection of electrons resulting from Pb-Pb collisions recorded in 2015 with the ALICE experiment at CERN [46], it is highlighted that around 900MeV there is a notable detection peak attributed to hadronic contamination (graphs below).

Briefly, there are some analogies between the production of pairs due to the collision of heavy ions such as Pb-Pb and that due to the collision of photons. For example, in both cases, the final act of the generation occurs from the vacuum [58, 59, 60]. From the calculations relating to our model, it emerges that the production of pairs starting from the conditions of stable, unperturbed equilibrium - that is in the hypothetical absence of any radiation or fluctuations - would occur at frequencies corresponding to an energy of 880 MeV, therefore close to the production peak attributed to hadronic contamination. In the reality, there are always energetic fluctuations, by which we justified in Methods the actual different energetic values at which is possible to get pairs. On 2025 we have published an article on Zenodo in which we show how hadrons could actually be considered as derived from the combination of a suitable number of real electrons and positrons [81]. Similar to the overlap of the leptons constituting an IA, they would partially overlap each other, giving rise to the apparition of quarks and gluons. If these considerations on hadrons were to prove coherent, it could mean that the hadronic contamination detected in the experiments could actually be due to an accentuated production of pairs, for energy values $E \approx 880 \text{ MeV}$ similar to those corresponding to the ultimate equilibrium frequency, which could be considered a sort of resonance frequency. It could in fact happen that the charged leptons, in the situation in which they are about to separate as described in this article, in particular energetic conditions quickly combine [81] to form the pions detected by the detector [46].

N Emergence of time, wave-particle dualism, neutrinos, transformation of the down quark into an up quark during neutron decay, quarks' mass from non-perturbative QCD dynamics, weak boson, dark matter, dark energy, entanglement and others. One of them consists in associating the field of the Immaterial Fluid in the hypothetical condition of stable, unperturbed equilibrium (without any kind of radiation or quantum fluctuations) to the Higgs field; and, similarly to other theories [53, 54], considering the Higgs boson as potentially made up of a proper combination of adjacent IAs.

O In fact, an experiment of this kind has already been conducted with positive results [92]. However, it was not technically possible to exclude with absolute certainty the influence of external factors or possible systematic errors. Still for technical reasons it was not even possible to perform the experiment on multiple dates or separate locations. In the article that describes the experiment [92], the theory that underlies is explained. It is been published with documentary value and as a stimulus for further investigations, but it cannot be considered scientifically founded. Given the relative simplicity of the experimental apparatus, it could be equally easy to reproduce the same experiment under controlled conditions, by appropriately modulating the physical parameters involved.

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